

RECONSTRUCTION IN CENTRAL AFRICA

"The true Imperialist . . . is kindled at times to ardour by the magnitude of his inheritance, and he has always, if he keeps the faith, optimism and hope to cheer him. But he is equally weighed down with the burden of his duties and the complexity of the task before him, if he would translate his dream into fact. A dependency to him is not a possession but a trust. The Glory of England is not in the mileage of her territory, but the state into which she is welding it."—JOHN BUCHAN, "A Lodge in the Wilderness."

"New demands have been made on the Treasury on every side. Everyone is demanding new conditions of life."—THE LORD CHANCELLOR (in the House of Lords), February 18th, 1919.

"The future is before us to make or mar . . . a new life, a new spirit is imperatively necessary, if Europe is not to fall backward . . . in the great march of humanity. . . . The spirit I am pleading for is that of openness of mind and willingness to learn and to try new methods. I see salvation for us and for the world only in a more human spirit and outlook all round."—GENERAL SMUTS' Farewell Message, July, 1919.

Now that the war is over it is time that serious consideration be paid to our duty and responsibility in Central Africa. We need a constructive policy, and that policy must be framed at home. (The direct responsibility for tropical administration will always rest with the Central Executive of the Empire. This cannot be delegated to local legislatures.) We want to try to steer clear of compromise so far as it is possible, and to initiate a policy that has a definite objective. This policy must be based on expert knowledge, for in our everyday life in Europe there is nothing applicable.

Money is needed, as I will endeavour to show, and must be forthcoming. As the British taxpayer will be called upon to find the money he is entitled to some guarantee that the money will be properly and economically spent. Therefore the first duty of the Government—its duty to Africa and its duty to the tax-payer—is to reform the African Civil Service.

Under the present system of separate and independent protectorates the proper control of such expenditure is impossible—it would be wasteful and disconnected, and would lack the definite aim that is essential to success.

A Central Government—co-ordinating but not amalgamating the Protectorates—under a High Commissioner with a staff of the very best men, is essential. This presents no difficulties. The men are available, and there are sufficient Central African statesmen in England to help the Colonial Office in their selection. There should be no delay about this; it must be done now. Africa is emerging from the melting pot, and the moulding should be done before it cools; therefore the men who are to do the moulding must be chosen forthwith, given adequate funds and be trusted.

Africa cannot develop properly without money, and in her present state of advancement she cannot find the money herself. In the interests of the black races, the white settlers and of humanity, we ought to get sanction now for the necessary expenditure.¹

It will not be an unproductive investment ultimately; indeed the return will, in the long run, be very great financially as well as morally, and will soon render unnecessary all "grants-in-aid"; but for the present this expenditure will bear no interest whatever. The ultimate benefit to the country and to the community is the justification for the proposal to spend large sums on social and other improvements at home; the same justification holds good in Africa; the claim for expenditure is just as sound and should not be passed over because the people for whom the claim is made have neither

¹ It is encouraging to read the following—spoken after this article was written—(Report from Lord Milner's speech at the East African Dinner, July 25th, 1919):—

"When they came to consider how far they had gone in developing material resources he thought that they were bound to admit that they were at a very early stage. The whole question was one of transportation, and that meant money. He maintained that in this instance the expenditure of money in the development of our Colonial possessions would be in every way an economical expenditure. (Cheers.) He believed in avoiding waste, but he remained unrepentantly convinced that a wise expenditure—an expenditure on development—was not waste but economy. (Cheers.) He felt that the Government could, and must, assist in that great necessary work."

vote nor voice. For the area between the Sudan and the Zambesi I reckon that thirty millions are needed in the next ten years. I will try to show why and how later, but if the reader will glance at a map he will realise at once that this claim is not at all excessive, for improved communications will take more than half, and without improved communications nothing can be done.

Apart from it being our duty to find this money, it is also sound policy, for, as the Under-Secretary of State for the Colonies said in the House of Commons (February 13th, 1919):

"We must consider possible opportunities for the State creating wealth quickly. There is a great field for the State in avenues where individual enterprise might not be tempted to venture."

Central Africa is essentially such a field, and in helping development there we shall help to make good the wastage of the war.

I will try to show first why it is our duty to find this money. Firstly, we owe it to humanity to justify our trusteeship. In the words quoted at the head of this article, "a dependency is not a possession but a trust." We must keep this before us or give up our dependencies. Secondly, we must not forget that the African natives concerned are members of the British Empire, and as such are entitled to share in our victory, especially as they played a leading part in that victory in Africa. Not only the troops that fought, and the hundreds of thousands who worked on supplies and communications, but the entire population, whose unswerving loyalty alone rendered our victory possible. It should not be lost sight of that this loyalty has been very real, and that the hardships of the war have been felt by them even far from the scene of hostilities, since all the goods which they purchase have (when still obtainable) increased enormously in price, often to a literally prohibitive figure, while their rate of wages has remained stationary and their opportunities for earning money have decreased. Thus the victory in Africa was a joint victory for white and black, and the white race must see to it that the black gets its reward.

Before considering the ways in which the money is needed

we should be clear on one point. There are two distinct problems in Africa: (1) The natives and their future; (2) the European settlers and their future; or the question of exploitation. It is a bigger matter than most people realise; and if it is to be boldly but sanely tackled, it needs a central authority over the existing protectorates. It would be the first duty of this central authority to think of all the protectorates as a whole, divide the problems of all into black and white—they will overlap in places—and decide *on the main lines* for action and give latitude for adaptation in different localities. I propose to deal here primarily with the native side, as the natives are inarticulate, though all the improvements suggested will benefit the Europeans too, either directly or indirectly; and part of the thirty millions will be needed for purely European requirements. Two quotations from Dudley Kidd's "Kafir Socialism," though written about South Africa, are very apposite here:—

"What we need is to consider the government of the Whites on its own merits, and that of the Kafirs also on its merits; if we separate entirely these two functions, we give to each race a chance to work out its own ideal."

"We should be very chary of seeking to draw up any uniform paper policy, to be applied with indiscriminating energy to all the different tribes. . . . It is not a cast-iron plan we need, but a master conception that might be developed differently in every district. If our policy is to succeed in a rough and ready workaday world, then it should have many seemingly illogical turns and twists—and a great capacity for adaptation—about it. We shall never solve the Kafir problem by geometry."

I repeat the men *are* available, and the task is not impossible. It has to be done some day, and postponement will only add immeasurably to the difficulty. But for the war we might have drifted on in the old way till the difficulties became insuperable; but this war has opened our eyes, and by putting Africa into the melting pot has given us the great chance of improving the state into which we are welding our dependencies.

What is the money wanted for? Thirty millions is not a small sum to be granted casually. No, nor is it a very big sum if one considers the area and the population concerned,

but an average of three millions a year for ten years is probably as much as could be controlled without waste.

First in importance, though not in amount, must come the Civil Service. The High Commissioner and the Central Government Staff must be well paid, so as to get the best men, and the whole of the existing civil services need reinforcing and invigorating. The present rate of pay and pensions is a disgrace to our Empire. This must be remedied at once. I place this first because without the proper machinery nothing else can be done—nothing else should be attempted, and we cannot get good machinery without paying for it. It need not be done in a "slap-dash" way, but it is a matter that needs tackling at once and generously. Adequate pay is always justified.

Granted that this is done 15 millions can be earmarked at once for communications. It would take a whole article of this length to deal with this adequately, and compression in this particular is impossible. Railways, roads, riverways, ports, harbours—all need co-ordinating and expanding. As for the amount suggested, let those who think it excessive ascertain the cost of Central African Railways and roads even at pre-war prices, and they will see that the estimate errs if anything on the side of moderation. This expenditure is absolutely necessary from every point of view. To put it briefly: (1) The necessity as regards our trust. It is no good starting to develop native industries and agriculture if we do not give the natives the means of marketing their produce. We must also make accessible the schools, colleges and hospitals that are to be built. (2) The necessity from the more material point of view of development and exploitation. Development cannot proceed without well-considered and boldly conceived expenditure on communications; and without development tropical Africa will be a burden to the Empire instead of an ever-increasing source of wealth. Africa resembles a mine in this respect; however rich the mine is, no wealth can be extracted from it without a large original expenditure; but "there is a bottom to every mine," whereas the wealth to be obtained from Africa will go on increasing always. One should never lose sight of the fact that there

has never yet been any effort made to allocate money systematically and wisely for tropical Africa; she has had to worry along with a few miserable doles—and doles spell waste. No business in the world can be run that way, and Africa is a business as well as a trust. After the experimental stage, at any rate, capital is required for any enterprise; and in Central Africa the time has come when capital is needed.¹ We cannot seriously consider wasting one of the biggest potential sources of wealth in the world for the sake of 30 millions. If it *were* a mine, with the endless wealth of Africa in view, the necessary capital would be subscribed at once.

Next in importance comes a largely increased medical service. I put this after the improved communications solely because to keep it within reasonable bounds the improved communications (railways, motor roads and motor-cycle paths, waterways, etc.) are absolutely necessary. But for this it would come second on the list, for one of our chief duties in Africa is to save life. The extent of unnecessary mortality and suffering is only credible to those who live among the natives.

(A large part of the expenditure on communications and improved medical services would be immediately productive to the Government in time-saving. Men could get about then more quickly, get away on leave more speedily, less reliefs for sickness, less wasted time and better work would also ensue.)

Fourthly, native education. The education of the native "became inevitable from the moment that he came into contact with the white man" (Lord Selborne—Address before the Cape University). It is we who have introduced a new European environment to which the native must adjust himself. Mere contact with Europeans educates (in its widest

¹ "We are at times too timid with respect to projects of development for fear of being accused of exploitation. Do not let us be deterred from doing what is right by ignorant clamour. It is our duty to the inhabitants of the countries themselves to help them to make better use of natural resources, often immense and almost completely neglected. In the process we inevitably enrich ourselves. Is that a reason for abstaining from it?"—Lord Milner at Oxford, Aug. 1, 1919. "We have been too timid in capitalising the territories under our control."—Colonel Amery in the House of Commons July 30, 1919.

sense) the natives; therefore it is the duty of the Europeans to build up a satisfactory system of native education. Without this we cannot justify our dependencies: without this nothing else avails. As Leibnitz said: "The masters of education hold in their hands the future of the world," but we must first get to know the natives, and we must also define what we mean by education for them; for whether it is to have a good or evil influence depends on the choice we make, and on the methods and the teachers we employ.

As regards the definition of native education, we should aim primarily at drawing out and developing the existing faculties; at teaching industries and not at creating an army of book-learners. The aims of Tuskegee and the Gordon College, Khartoum, should be before us always. I propose to quote from a few writers who have considered this problem seriously:—

"We believe that our young people should be taught the fundamental industries—trades, agriculture, and household economy—regardless of mental training."—BOOKER WASHINGTON, 1905.

"Above all, teach them trades and handicrafts and the simple laws of decent life."—JOHN BUCHAN, "A Lodge in the Wilderness."

"Industrial and agricultural education should be essential features in native education, not mere adjuncts thereto. Otherwise it is to be feared that we will only succeed in causing dissatisfaction and discontent."—A. COLQUHOUN, "The Africander Land."

"The primary objects of native education must be the development of intelligence, the training of character, and in particular the promotion of industry."—Cape Select Committee on Native Education, 1908.

"Any system of instruction . . . which gives the natives a literary and bookish education, as the present system does, when the work which the natives will be required to do will be, for the most part, industrial and agricultural, would be doing the native more harm than good."—C. T. LORAM, "The Education of the S. African Native."

"On the necessity of industrial training for the natives of South Africa there is a remarkable unanimity. Government Commissioners and officials, missionaries, students of the Native Question and the general public all agree that industrial training should be made a chief end of native education."—*Ibid.*

We want to turn the natives into useful and contented citizens of our Empire. Citizenship is the antithesis of slavery, and we cannot really claim to have abolished the latter until

we have given the former to the natives. This is only possible by sympathetic government, assistance and education. Mental growth is directed and encouraged by use; it is for us to supply the direction and encouragement.

Capable teachers are necessary, and they must work under a State Education Department. That is to say, the main work of education must be the duty of the State. The work being done by the missions can continue, and can be further encouraged (though some compulsory qualifications for teachers are necessary), and a Missionary Board of Advice will be necessary to help the Department by making accessible their experience. Two quotations will suffice to support this claim (neither author is in any way "anti-missionary") :—

"We are dealing with the most difficult of all problems, the government and progress of a backward race, and we allow the most inefficient teachers, whose only qualification for the difficult work is their own kind hearts, to form the character of the rising generation and to complicate immensely our difficulties. We might as well try to cure cancer by kindness as to educate savages by it. The quality of the education we give to the Kafirs, probably more than anything else, decides the future of the natives: and yet while there are many excellent native schools, we also allow the most inefficient people to miseducate the Kafirs. . . . Has a state the right to *allow* unqualified people to intensify national problems in this gratuitous fashion? The future of the Kafirs is, in some cases, being decided by people of the narrowest outlook."—DUDLEY KRDD, "Kafir Socialism."

"No restrictions have been placed upon the work of a missionary, with the result that a number of men, unfitted by nature and training, or lack of training, have taken up mission work. In the writer's opinion missionaries and teachers should be required to take out a licence before they are allowed to practise among the natives. It is highly desirable that the Government should know who are educating the native people. . . . At present it is possible for anyone to open a school for the natives without notifying the authorities. . . . A great deal of incompetent teaching is being carried on."—C. T. LORAM, "The Education of the S. African Native."

A great deal that one hears against native education, and against educated natives, is due to the education being on wrong lines, and—in some cases, not by any means in all—to the unqualified people by whom natives are "educated." We cannot deny education to the natives; we cannot condemn them to stagnation and bar their chance of progress for ever;

but we do need a first-class Department of Native Education. It is not a matter about which we should take hurried ill-considered action, but it needs starting at once; and it needs money. One of the chief reasons why industrial training has been neglected is the expense entailed.

"The education of the . . . natives is the duty of the State, and the expense involved must be regarded as a legitimate charge against State funds."—C. T. LORAM, "The Education of the S. African Native."

Fifthly, as a natural corollary to education, we must encourage native industries; resuscitate and revive the dying and dead native industries and start new ones. I have no space to dilate upon this now, but the matter is one of great urgency, and is quite essential to progress in Central Africa.

There are many other matters that could be mentioned which need a settled policy and their share of the thirty millions, but they cannot be touched upon here. I trust, however, that enough has been said to prove the contentions made at the beginning of this article—namely, that the natives of Central Africa have a right to demand new conditions of life, and that it is our duty to grant them these conditions. That to do this we must allot an adequate sum and provide the machinery for its profitable expenditure.

Finally, I would urge that this is a matter which is the direct concern of every Briton, and not only of the few who have hitherto been interested in Africa. If any matter is the duty of Great Britain it is equally the duty of each and all of her citizens. The hardest thing with which we "Africans" have to contend is the apathy of the majority of our countrymen on matters African. This apathy is extremely shortsighted, for Africa is going to be of the utmost importance to our Empire and to the world during the next century, and we should always "Keep open our communications with the future."¹

AFRICANUS.

¹ John Buchan, "The African Colony."